

First record of *Pompilocalus* sp. Roig Alsina, 1989 (Hymenoptera: Pompilidae) preying on *Tachymenis chilensis coronellina* (Werner, 1898) (Serpentes: Dipsadidae) from Central Chile

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Tachymenis chilensis coronellina is a dipsadid snake distributed from the southern part of the Atacama Desert south (Atacama Region) to San Fernando (O'Higgins Region) (Ortiz, 1973; Valenzuela-Dellarossa et al., 2010). The current taxonomic status is as a subspecies endemic to central Chile (Ruiz de Gamboa, 2016), although some authors have considered it to be a full species (e.g. Valenzuela-Dellarossa, 2016); the nominate subspecies *T. chilensis chilensis* is found from Monte Lorenzo and Toquihua (O'Higgins Region) to Chiloé Island (Los Lagos Region) in Chile (Ortiz, 1973; Simonetti, 2001; Valenzuela-Dellarossa et al., 2010) and, it is cited from Neuquén, Chubut and Río Negro provinces in adjacent Argentina (Avila et al., 2012; Giraudo et al., 2012; Nenda et al., 2017). In this work, we maintain the subspecies status (*sensu* Valenzuela-Dellarossa et al., 2010; Ruiz de Gamboa, 2016). This snake is active during spring near lagoons and small water courses, where it forages for amphibians, which are captured and subdued using a combination of constriction and venom (Greene and Jaksic, 1992; Donoso-Barros, 1962).

The ectoparasitoid wasps of the family Pompilidae capture and paralyze spiders, and their larvae feed on the encapsulated spider (De la Fuente Coello, 2000; Fernández and Pujade-Villar, 2015). Five species of

uncertain taxonomic status in the genus *Pompilocalus* are found in Chile, all of similar appearance and coloration (Roig-Alsina, 1989; Silva et al., 2015). In central Chile, female *Pompilocalus* wasps can be observed searching for nesting sites and capturing mygalomorph spiders during spring (Jaffuel and Piri6n, 1926; Claude-Joseph, 1930).

Here, we describe a *Pompilocalus* sp. opportunistically depredating a live, injured *T. c. coronellina*. At 12:30 h on November 8th, 2018, during a fieldwork at El Sauce (-33.8691°N, -71.3913°W, WGS84; elevation 127

Figure 1. A) Site of the observation El Sauce, Melipilla, B) *Pompilocalus* sp. wasp preying on *Tachymenis chilensis coronellina*.

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m), sector San Pedro, Melipilla, Metropolitan Region, Chile, an adult (> 15 cm in length) *T. c. coronellina* was observed on the edge of a road with serious damage to its body after having been run over by a car (Fig. 1). Shortly thereafter, a wasp was observed dragging the snake from the road towards the roadside vegetation. The specimens were not captured. Based on Roig-Alsina (1989) and Vardy (2002), we identified the wasp as belonging to the genus *Pompilocalus*. We are unable to say whether the *Pompilocalus* wasp was feeding on or parasitizing the snake; however, scavenging a living vertebrate from roadway is an unusual observation that to our knowledge has not previously been described.

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